

APPLYING VARIOUS TEACHING METHODS IN CLASSES FOR MIXED-ABILITY STUDENTS

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14208954>

Saidrasulova Shaxnoza Nazarovna

Senior teacher of Foreign Languages Department,
Journalism and Mass Communications University of Uzbekistan.

ABSTRACT

The primary aim of this article is to present a method for teaching English in mixed-ability classes. This approach, based on my teaching experience, emphasizes simultaneously focusing on both syntagmatic and paradigmatic language relations. Although memorizing lengthy vocabulary lists and teaching grammatical rules can often be seen as tedious, they remain essential for learners. Given that there is a significant amount of material to cover in a limited time, reading texts are broken down into phrasal-level syntagms. As a pre-reading activity, students receive lists of these syntagms along with their meanings in their native language. Using the students' native language helps create a comfortable environment, allowing them to build self-confidence while engaging with the target language. The list is reviewed and partly memorized in a session, ensuring that students face no difficulties with pronunciation and grammatical structures. It's important to recognize that human experience lies at the heart of all linguistic activities, and the teacher's personality plays a vital role in this process..

Keywords: *differentiated instruction, learning styles, mixed ability classes, multiple intelligences, vocabulary learning*

Although it's now widely accepted that learners have different learning styles, approaches like one-size-fits-all instruction based on age and grade levels, whole-class lectures, and uniform progress still remain the standard, even in today's evolving educational landscape. [Hess, 1999; Sizer, 1999]. Nonetheless, as a glance through a typical classroom setting reveals, invisible diversities of learning characteristics and preferences dominate the ELT practices all over the globe. Some students come to school with little support and encouragements from home, while others commence the learning process, with skills and knowledge years beyond grade level expectations (Tomlinson, 1999). As Caine and Caine (1990) note, “There can be up to a five-year difference in maturation between any two „average“ children” (p. 2). It is important to make a clear distinction between mixed ability teaching and mixed ability classes. Most teachers have to teach mixed ability groups but they not be using mixed ability teaching

strategies. McKeown (2004) believes that Many teachers view a mixed-ability class as a group of average and capable students, along with a subset of learners who face learning challenges.. Ireson & Hallam (2001) suggest Teachers need to acknowledge that a class is mixed-ability because students possess different strengths and weaknesses and progress at varying rates. They also have diverse preferences for learning and showcasing their work. One effective metaphor for understanding a mixed-ability class is to imagine the class as an elevator, with students moving at different speeds everyone starts by getting into the elevator. Some students will eagerly rush in, while others may need a bit of encouragement. Some will reach the top floor, others might stop at the third floor, and a few may only make it to the first floor, but all will have made progress in their own way. By the end of the class, every student should leave feeling challenged and proud of their accomplishments.

It's important to caution against a common misconception some teachers have about genuinely implementing differentiated instruction. Often, teachers may claim to be practicing differentiation, but in reality, they are merely following traditional teaching methods. "Mixed ability" is a proposed term intended to replace outdated labels such as disabled, handicapped, abnormal, and crippled. This term encompasses individuals with varying physical abilities, as well as those with distinct emotional or learning capabilities. Historically, terms like disabled, crippled, and handicapped have carried negative connotations and perpetuated stigma. In contrast, "mixed ability" modernizes the terminology used to describe those with different or medically documented physical or mental attributes, aiming to diminish social stigma and foster more inclusive conversations. By adopting this more positive and respectful language, society can better recognize the diversity of abilities among individuals and promote a greater understanding and acceptance of all people, regardless of their unique challenges or strengths.

The teacher may claim to be using differentiated instruction, but in reality, they are simply adhering to traditional teaching methods. This is evident in a study by Blozowich (2001) who found that teachers used a variety of techniques but continued to prepare lessons as they would for a tracked classroom. The researcher concluded that teachers applying differentiated instruction require ongoing and consistent professional development, as well as in-depth discussions on how to effectively implement these techniques in the classroom. Among the other supportive claims in favor of the privileges of differentiated instruction, reference can be made to McAdamis (2001) work, which pointed to significant performance enhancement among the students in the Rockwood School District (Missouri), successive to the implementation of differentiated instruction. This study identifies planning, mentoring, professional development, conducting action research, and organizing

workshops as the primary strategies to help reduce teachers' initial resistance to differentiation in education. Additionally, another study explores the effects of implementing differentiated syllabi for teachers. Affholder (2003) found that teachers who made an intensive use of these strategies developed a better individual perception and assumed greater responsibility for student growth. Moreover, consistent with the findings of this study, teachers who frequently employed differentiated techniques in their classrooms demonstrated higher levels of self-efficacy and a greater willingness to experiment with new instructional methods. Yet, as the results revealed, those enjoying seniority and higher experience were found to be at a more privileged position in this respect. Working with the unique community of undergraduate teachers, Johnsen (2003) concluded that the use of differentiated techniques proved to be a beneficial tool in keeping the individuals“ interested and, consequently, the implemented techniques were said to have provided the undergraduate teachers with a highly gratifying experience. Additionally, establishing a structured classroom management system creates a sense of security and clarity, allowing students to focus on learning without distractions. As a positive role model, you can inspire and motivate students to develop their own enthusiasm for learning. Here are some specific strategies tailored for different age groups that can effectively promote these principles.

REFERANCES

1. Abdujabarova, K. H. K. (2021). USE OF FICTION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS'SPEECH ACTIVITIES IN PRACTICAL CLASSES. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 1(8), 241-245.
2. Affholder, L. P. (2003). Differentiated instruction in inclusive elementary classrooms. University of Kansas, Kansas
3. Hallam, S., & Toutounji, I (1996). What Do We Know about The Grouping of Pupils by Ability? London: Institute of Education.
4. Johnsen, S. (2003). Adapting instruction with heterogeneous groups. *Gifted Child Today*, 26 (3), 5-6.
5. Khasanova, G. K. (2023). ASSESSMENT CRITERIA OF ORGANIZATIONAL-MANAGERIAL COMPETENCES OF MASTER'S STUDENTS. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(22), 24-29.
6. McKeown, S. (2004). Meeting SEN in the Curriculum: Modern Foreign Languages. London: David Fulton Publishers

7. Saidrasulova, S. N. (2022). CONCEPTUAL APPROACHES TO THE STUDY OF CULTURE. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(Special Issue 20), 671-675.
8. Saidova, Z. U., & Sultanova, D. B. (2023). DEVELOPMENT OF COMPETENCIES FOR STUDENTS’SELF-STUDY IN A CREDIT-MODULE SYSTEM AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 3(22), 109-112.
9. Urakovna, S. Z. (2022). THE USE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN THE FORMATION OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES OF ESP STUDENTS.
10. Yunusova, Z. (2022). Teaching English for specific purposes and its types. *Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(Special Issue 27), 106-109.